

APPROXIMATE SOLUTION OF A ONE-DIMENSIONAL FREDHOLM SYSTEM OF INTEGRAL EQUATIONS OF THE SECOND KIND USING NUMERICAL METHODS

Abirayev Imomali ^{1,a}
Nematullayeva Gulshana ^{2,b}

¹ Denau institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

² 2nd year master, Denau institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy
Denau, Uzbekistan

^a ustozmat616@gmail.com, ^b agmandinova@gmail.com

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Abstract

We consider the solution of a one-dimensional Fredholm system of integral equations of the second kind by combining numerical methods, iterative and optimal coefficient methods, and studying the solution of the following Fredholm system of integral equations:

$$y_i(x) = f_i(x) + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^q \int_0^1 K_{ij}(x, t) y_j(t) dt, \quad i = \overline{1, q}. \quad (1.1)$$

In the system of equations (1.1), let the free terms and kernels satisfy the following conditions:

$$f_i(x) \in E_1^\alpha(C_1), \quad K_{ij}(x, t) \in E_2^\alpha(C_2) \quad (i, j = \overline{1, 2, \dots, q}). \quad (1.2)$$

We will seek the solution of system (1.1) in the form of a Neumann series:

$$y_i(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda^n \varphi_{in}(x) \quad (i = \overline{1, q}). \quad (1.3)$$

Here, λ is a small parameter, and the functions must be determined.

By substituting (1.3) into (1.1), integrating, and summing instead of integrating (since the regularity of such substitution is difficult to justify), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \lambda^n \varphi_{ij}(x) = \\ & = f_i(x) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^q \lambda^n \int_0^1 K_{ij}(x, t) \varphi_{j, n-1}(x) \quad (i = \overline{1, q}) \end{aligned} \quad (1.4)$$

Equating the coefficients of equal powers of λ and making some transformations, we get

$$\varphi_{i0}(x) = f_i(x),$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{in}(x) &= \int_{G_n} \sum_{j_1, \dots, j_n}^q K_{ij_1}(x, t_1) \prod_{l=2}^n K_{j_{l-1}j_l}(t_{l-1}t_l) \times \\ &\times f_{j_n}(t_n) dt_1 \dots dt_n \end{aligned} \quad (1.5)$$

Taking into account the expression (3.6), we obtain:

$$\varphi_{in}(x) = \int_{G_n} \varphi_{in}(x, t) dt$$

Let

$$\begin{aligned} A &= 2^{\alpha+1} \left(3 + \frac{2}{\alpha-1} \right) \\ |\lambda| &< \left(\frac{3\alpha q A^2 C_2}{2(\alpha-1)} \right)^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

We determine the natural numbers N_1 and M as follows:

$$N_1 = \lceil N^{\frac{1}{2}} \log \frac{-\beta N}{2} \rceil, \quad M = \lceil \frac{(\alpha-1) \log N - (\alpha\beta - \beta + 2) \log \log N}{2(\log \log N - \log(|\lambda| q A^2 C_2))} \rceil. \quad (1.6)$$

Then the following theorem holds:

Theorem 1. $N \geq 2^\alpha$, $\alpha > 1$, and inequality (1.3) is satisfied, then for the solution of system (1.1) the following equality is valid:

$$y_i(x) = f_i(x) + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) + R_N, \quad i = \overline{1, q}. \quad (1.7)$$

Here

$$R_N = 0DN^{-\frac{\alpha-1}{2}} \log^{0.5\beta+M-1} N, \quad |0| < 1,$$

$D = D(\alpha, \lambda, q, A, C_1, C_2)$ – constant.

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P r o o f. According to V.S.Ryabenko, we define the trigonometric polynomial $P_{inN_1}(x, t)$ by the following equality:

$$\hat{C}_i(x, m) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) e^{-2\pi i \frac{(m,a)k}{N}}, \tag{1.8}$$

$$P_{inN_1}(x, t) = \sum_{k(m) < N_1} \hat{C}_i(x, m) e^{2\pi i(m,t)} \tag{1.9}$$

Substituting (1.8) into (1.9), we obtain

$$P_{inN_1}(x, t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) \psi_{kn}(t), \tag{1.10}$$

where

$$\psi_{kn}(t) = \sum_{k(m) < N_1} e^{2\pi i(m,t - \frac{\alpha k}{N})} \tag{1.11}$$

Now, the function $\Phi_{in}(x, t)$ can be written as follows:

$$\Phi_{in} = \Phi_{in}(x, t) = P_{knN_1}(x, t) + r_{inN_1}(x, t). \tag{1.12}$$

Using the equalities (1.4) - (1.6) and (1.10) - (1.12) we can express equation (1.3) in the following form:

$$y_i(x) = f_i(x) + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n g_{knN_1} \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) + \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n R_{inN_1}(x) + \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} \lambda^n \varphi_{in}(x), \tag{1.13}$$

where

$$R_{inN_1}(x) = \int_{G_n} r_{inN_1}(x, t) dt, \tag{1.14}$$

$$\begin{aligned} g_{knN_1} &= \int_{G_n} \psi_{knN_1}(t) dt = \sum_{k(m) < N_1} \int_{G_n} e^{2\pi i(m,t - \frac{\alpha k}{N})} dt = \\ &= \sum_{k(m) < N_1} e^{2\pi i(m, \frac{\alpha k}{N})} \int_{G_n} e^{2\pi i(m,t)} dt = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Now, in equation (1.13), we deal with the last two summations.

Let the coefficients $C_{ir}(x, m)$ and $C_{i\Phi}(x, m)$ define corresponding Fourier functions $r_{inN_1}(x, t)$ and $\Phi_{in}(x, t)$ respectively. Then we have:

$$r_{inN_1}(x, t) = \sum_m C_{ir}(x, m) e^{2\pi i(m,t)} \tag{1.15}$$

$$\Phi_{in}(x, t) = \sum_m C_{i\Phi}(x, m) e^{2\pi i(m,t)} \tag{1.16}$$

Here, \sum_m - represents the summation over all points in the n -dimensional space. From equations (1.9) and (1.12), we obtain the necessary relations for the trigonometric approximation of the system.

We have the equality

$$C_{ir}(x, m) = \begin{cases} C_{i\Phi}(x, m) - c_1(x, m), & \text{if } K(m) < N_1 \\ C_{i\Phi}(x, m), & \text{if } K(m) \geq N_1 \end{cases}$$

Using equations (1.15) - (1.16) and substituting into (1.14), taking the last ratio into account, we obtain

$$|R_{inN_1}(x)| \leq \sum_{K(m) < N_1} |C_{i\Phi}(x, m) - C_1(x, m)| + \sum_{K(m) \geq N_1} |C_{i\Phi}(x, m)|. \quad (1.17)$$

To estimate the first sum, we modify Lemma 8. However, since n is a varying quantity, we must determine the relationship between the constants C_0, C_1 and $C = C_0^\alpha + nB^n$ with respect to n .

Here

$$B < 3 + \frac{2}{\alpha-1}.$$

According to the definition of the optimal coefficient (Lemma 2), we have

$$C_0 = C_{-0} < 2 \left(2 + \frac{3}{\log N} \right)^n$$

$$\Phi_{in}(x, t) \in E n_n^\alpha (q^n A^n C_2^n C_1).$$

$$C = C_1 (q A C_2)^n. \quad (1.18)$$

It is not difficult to see that

$$e^{-2\pi i(m,t)} \in E_n^\alpha (N_1^\alpha) \quad \text{in every } K(m) < N$$

Now, replacing the function $\Phi_{in}(x,t)e^{-2\pi i(m,t)}$ according to Lemma 9, we obtain

$$|C_{i\Phi}(x, m) - C_i(x, m)| =$$

$$= \left| \int_{G_n} \Phi_{in}(x, t) e^{-2\pi i(m,t)} dt - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) e^{-\frac{2\pi i k}{N}} \right| \leq$$

$$\leq C_1 (q A C_2)^n A N_1^\alpha N^{-\alpha} (C_0^\alpha + nB^n) \log^{\alpha\beta} N_1.$$

It is clear that for any $N \geq 2^\alpha$

$$C_0^\alpha + nB^n < A^n \left[\frac{n}{2^{n(\alpha+1)}} + \frac{\left(2 + \frac{3}{\log N} \right)^{\alpha n}}{2^{\alpha n} \left(3 + \frac{2}{\alpha+1} \right)^n} \right] < A^n.$$

$$|C_{i\Phi}(x, m) - C_i(x, m)| \leq C_i A (q A^2 C_2)^n N_1^\alpha N^{-\alpha} \log^{\alpha\beta} N_1.$$

Using this estimate and the fact that

$$\sum_{K(m) < N_1} 1 \leq 3^n N_1 \log^{n-1} N_1$$

$$\sum_{K(m) < N_1} |C_{i\Phi}(x, m) - C_{i\Phi}(x, m)| \leq C_i A (3 q A^2 C_2)^n N_1^{\alpha+1} N^{-\alpha} \log^{\alpha\beta+n-1} N_1$$

To estimate the second sum in expression (1.17), we use Lemma 3, Which gives

$$\sum_{K(m) \geq N_1} |C_{i\Phi}(x, m)| \leq 3^n C_1 (q A C_2)^n \alpha \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha-1} \right)^n N_1^{-\alpha+1} \log^{n-1} N_1$$

Hense,

$$|R_{inN_1}(x)| \leq C_1(qAC_2)^n \left(A^{n+1}N_1^{\alpha+1}N^{-\alpha} \log^{\alpha\beta+n-1}N_1 + \alpha \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha-1}\right)^n N_1^{-\alpha+1} \log^{n-1}N_1 \right).$$

Recalling the definition of N_1 and after some substitutions, we obtain

$$\left| \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n R_{inN_1}(x) \right| \leq C_1 N^{-\frac{\alpha}{2} + \frac{1}{2}} \log^{0,5(\alpha-1)\beta+M-1} N \left[\frac{2A}{2^{\alpha\beta}} \sum_{n=1}^M \left(\frac{3|\lambda|qA^2C_2}{2} \right)^n + 2\alpha \sum_{n=1}^M \left(\frac{3|\lambda|qA^2C_2}{2(\alpha-1)} \right)^n \right] \leq 3|\lambda|qA^2C_1C_2 \left[\frac{2\alpha^2}{2(\alpha-1) - 3|\lambda|qA^2C_2} + \frac{2^{1-\alpha\beta}A}{2 - 3|\lambda|qA^2C_2} \right] N^{-\frac{\alpha-1}{2}} g^{0,5(\alpha-1)\beta+M-1} N. \tag{1.18}$$

Taking into account (1.18), we estimate the last series in (1.17):

$$\left| \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} \lambda^n \varphi_{in}(x) \right| = \left| \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} \lambda^n \int_{G_n} \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} \lambda^n \varphi_{in}(x, t) dt \right| \leq \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} |\lambda|^n \sum_m \frac{(qAC_2)^n C_1}{K(m)^\alpha} \leq C_1 \sum_{n=M+1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^\alpha} (|\lambda|qA^2C_2)^n = C_1 \frac{(|\lambda|qA^2C_2)^{M+1}}{2^\alpha(1 - |\lambda|qA^2C_2)}. \tag{1.19}$$

Combining estimates (1.18) - (3.27) and recalling the meaning of M , we have

$$y_i(x) = f_i(x) + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) + R_N,$$

$$R_N = \theta DN^{-\frac{\alpha-1}{2}} \log^{0,5\beta+M-1} N, \quad |\theta| < 1$$

$$D = |\lambda|qA^2C_1C_2 \left[\frac{6\alpha^2}{2(\alpha-1) - 3\alpha|\lambda|qA^2C_2} + \frac{6(2^{-\alpha\beta}A)}{2 - 3|\lambda|qA^2C_2} + \frac{1}{1 - |\lambda|qA^2C_2} \right].$$

Thus, Theorem 1 is proved.

As an example, consider the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} y_1(x) = f_1(x) + \lambda \int_0^1 [K_{11}(x, t)y_1(t) + K_{12}(x, t)y_2(t)] dt \\ y_2(x) = f_2(x) + \lambda \int_0^1 [K_{21}(x, t)y_1(t) + K_{22}(x, t)y_2(t)] dt \end{cases}$$

Here

$$K_{11}(x, t) = \sin 2\pi(x + t), \quad K_{12}(x, t) = \sin 2\pi(x - t)$$

$$K_{21}(x, t) = \cos 2\pi(x + t) \quad K_{22}(x, t) = \cos 2\pi(x - t)$$

$$f(x) = \sin 2\pi x - \frac{\lambda}{2^{0.5}} \sin(2\pi x + \frac{\pi}{4})$$

$$f(x) = \cos 2\pi x - \frac{\lambda}{2^{0.5}} \cos(2\pi x + \frac{\pi}{4})$$

It is not difficult to verify that the exact solution of this system is:

$$y(x) = \sin 2\pi x; \quad y(x) = \cos 2\pi x$$

$$y_i(x) = f_i(x) + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}),$$

Here $\Phi_{in}(x,t)$ and M_{kn} are defined by the formula (1.1). For the errors we obtain

$$R_{in} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^M \lambda^n \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_{in}(x, M_{kn}) - \frac{\lambda}{2^{0.5}} \sin(2\pi x + \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\pi}{2} i)$$

Table 1

X1	X2	M	N	LAM	R1 (X)	R2 (X)
0.20	0.50	2	8	0.01	0.112265D-02	0.725872D-05
0.99	0.9	2	8	0.01	0.300380D-02	0.172733D-04
0.2	0.9	3	8	0.01	0.630671D-02	0.127690D-04
0.2	0.9	2	8	0.1	0.636336D-01	0.127316D-02
0.2	0.9	2	8	0.001	0.110780D-03	0.725872D-05
0.2	0.9	3	8	0.1	0.636862D-01	0.131053D-02
0.2	0.9	3	16	0.01	0.629164D-02	0.145131D-04
0.2	0.9	4	60	0.01	0.629338D-02	0.148427D-04

The table shows the values of x, M, N, λ and errors R_1 and R_2 , corresponding to the approximate solutions $y_1(x)$ va $y_2(x)$.

The table shows that this algorithm performs well even for the small values of N .

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